

Investigating the role of dispersion corrections and anharmonic effects on the phase transition of SrZrS₃: A systematic analysis from AIMD free energy calculations

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The thermally driven needle-like (NL) to distorted perovskite (DP) phase transition was investigated by means of ab initio free energy calculations accelerated using machine learning for SrZrS₃, a prototypical composition of chalcogenide perovskites. As a first step, a systematic screening of the methods to include long-range interactions in semilocal DFT PBE calculations was performed. Out of the 8 correction schemes tested, the TS/HI method was found to yield the best match between lattice geometries and experimental reference, while predicting the correct order of stability of NL and DP phases at zero temperature. This method was then used in free energy calculations, performed using several approaches, so as to determine the effect of diverse anharmonicity contributions, such as the anisotropic thermal lattice expansion or the thermally induced internal structure changes, on the phase transition temperature ($T_{NP \rightarrow DP}$). Accounting for the full anharmonicity by combining the *NPT* MD data with thermodynamic integration with harmonic reference provided our best estimate of $T_{NL \rightarrow DP} = 867$ K. Although this result underestimates the reference experimental data by ~ 150 K, it still provides an improvement by nearly 300 K compared to previous theoretical report by Koocher et al. (Inorg. Chem. 62, 11134–11141 (2023)).

I. INTRODUCTION

Chalcogenide perovskites (CP), with ABX_3 composition (A and B are metal cations and $X = S, Se$), have been recently identified as better alternatives for halide perovskites in terms of chemical and thermal stability and, for suitable choice of A and B, also a low toxicity¹⁻⁴. Several recently published experimental and theoretical studies have demonstrated the potential of these materials in a variety of applications by offering new insights into their syntheses, fundamental opto-electronic properties and an understanding on the effect of different thermodynamic conditions.⁵⁻¹¹ Similar to their halide counterparts, these materials also exist in several competing crystal phases differing in arrangement of BX_6 octahedral framework.^{3,12} The two most prominent phases are the needle perovskite (NL) in the NH_4CdCl_3 -type structures (see Fig. 1) and the distorted perovskite phase (DP) in the $GdFeO_3$ structure. Both phases form crystals with orthorhombic symmetry (space group $Pnma$) but they significantly differ in internal structures. In particular, the NL phase consists of mutually unbound one-dimensional chains of edge-sharing octahedra, while the DP phase comprises a three-dimensional network of corner-sharing octahedra.

So far, most of the CP compositions, which have been experimentally synthesized, such as $BaZrS_3$, $CaZrS_3$, $SrTiS_3$, $BaHfS_3$, $SrHfS_3$, and $EuHfS_3$ ^{5,13,14}, are found to preferably exist in the DP phase. However, according to the experimental report by Lee et al., $SrZrS_3$ is found to occur in both of these aforementioned phases depending on the temperature (T) of synthesis.¹⁴ A first order phase transformation is observed from the low T NL phase to the high T DP phase at 1253 K during heating and reverse transformation from DP to NL at 1023 K.¹⁴ Importantly, although NL is the thermodynamically stable phase at room T , it is possible to synthesize DP at the same conditions as a long-lived metastable phase.^{5,14} Another prominent phase transition which has been observed in $SrZrS_3$ is the one where the DP phase further transforms quasi-continuously to the undistorted parent cubic phase (C) at $\sim 1200-1500$ K.^{6,7} Such a continuous phase transition, which only causes deformation and local rearrangements within the cell without breaking and forming bonds, could be investigated using straightforward ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD), as reported earlier^{6,7}. However, unlike the DP \rightarrow C phase transformation, structural conversion from the NL to DP phase at high T can only oc-

FIG. 1. Crystal structures of SrZrS_3 : NL phase projected onto the a - c crystal plane (left), and DP phase projected onto the b - c plane (right). Note that the 1D chain comprising the structure of NL is parallel with the crystal b axis. The blue, gray, and saffron colored spheres represent the Sr, Zr, and S atoms, respectively, while the black solid lines denote the supercells used in calculations consisting of $2 \times 4 \times 1$ (NL) and $2 \times 2 \times 2$ (DP) multiples of conventional orthorhombic cell (space group $Pnma$).

cur through bond reorganization owing to the different octahedral connectivity of the phases. The latter implies that the phase transition involves high free energy barriers, making such a process a rare event¹⁵ that cannot be accessed via straightforward AIMD simulations with the CPU power available today. Such phase transitions are therefore studied without explicitly considering the transition mechanism. Assuming thermodynamic equilibrium, the latter can be achieved by investigating the relative phase stability determined by suitably chosen thermodynamic potential, such as the Gibbs free energy (G) in the case of setting with fixed number of particles, temperature and pressure (NPT ensemble).

Various methods have been proposed to calculate G . The most popular and relatively inexpensive method is the quasi-harmonic approximation (QHA)^{16,17} which describes anharmonicity only partly, by including volume dependencies of vibrational frequencies. Although the QHA method has been successfully used to study thermal properties of various materials,^{18,19} this approach has proven to be inadequate in many cases, mainly at high T , where anharmonicity becomes important.^{20,21} Another way to treat anharmonicity is by including higher order anharmonic terms in the Taylor expansion

of the potential energy or via a self-consistent approach non-perturbatively. Methods such as temperature dependent effective potential (TDEP),²² self-consistent phonon theory (SCPH),²³ stochastic self-consistent harmonic approximation (SSCHA)²⁴ and the velocity auto-correlation function from molecular dynamics trajectories²⁵ have been developed based on this approach.^{26–28}

In the context of free energy calculations, molecular dynamics (MD) methods are highly pertinent because they naturally involve all anharmonicity effects. One of the most popular MD-based methods to study phase transitions^{29–32} without the need to define reversible transformation path in configuration space is the thermodynamic integration with harmonic reference (TI).^{33,34} Unfortunately, such calculations are severely limited due to their high computational cost when linked with *ab initio* level of theory. The recent advances in adaptive the machine learning force fields³¹ (MLFF) make these demanding simulations more easily available for routine calculations. Example of successful combination of AIMD-based TI calculation with MLFF is the recent investigation of phase transitions in inorganic halide perovskites by Fransson et al.³²

In addition to selecting an appropriate method to calculate the free energy, another challenge is to choose a suitable functional that can correctly describe long-range dispersive interactions. Including these interactions is crucial for accurate calculation of the structure and energetics, especially in perovskites, which consist of highly polarizable atoms. This has been extensively demonstrated for various compositions of halide perovskites.^{35–37} Egger et al.³⁵, for instance, investigated the role of Van der Waals (vdW) corrections for MAPbX₃ (X=Cl, Br, I) using the PBE+TS dispersion scheme and inferred that such corrections cause a significant contraction of the unit cell compared to the one predicted by PBE, leading to better estimates of structural parameters. Similar observations for CP were also presented in our previous report⁶, where the inclusion of a D3 dispersion correction in the functional PBE significantly improved structural descriptions at finite temperatures. However, as we shall show, employing the D3 corrections reverses the order of stability of the NL and DP phase, which is inconsistent with experimental observation. Hence, the choice of an appropriate functional that correctly predicts both structure and energies of well-known phases in CPs is still an open question requiring attention.

In this study, we systematically analyze the role of two important factors that con-

tribute to accurate prediction of phase transition temperature in SrZrS_3 , which are the role of long-range dispersion interactions and the importance of anharmonic effects in free energy calculations. This paper is organized as follows: the methodology used in this work is described in section II, the results of screening of dispersion correction methods are presented in section III A, schemes for including different types of anharmonic contributions to free energy are discussed in section III B, our theoretical predictions of transition temperature are confronted with experimental data in section IV, and a summary of the most important results is given in section V.

II. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS

A. Structural relaxation and vibrational analysis

Ab initio simulations were employed within periodic density functional theory (DFT), as implemented in VASP software package^{38–40}. The Kohn-Sham equations were solved using the projected augmented wave (PAW) method of Blöchl.⁴¹ The exchange-correlation energy was treated with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional⁴² within the generalized gradient approximation. The kinetic energy cut-off to the plane-wave basis set was set to 400 eV and convergence threshold for the electronic energies was set to 10^{-6} eV. To account for the long range Van der Waals (vdW) interactions, various popular schemes of dispersion corrections were employed, namely, D2⁴³, D3 with zero-damping function (D3(0)) and Becke-Johnson damping (D3(BJ)), as proposed by Grimme⁴⁴, Tkatchenko-Scheffler (TS) method⁴⁵, Tkatchenko-Scheffler method with iterative Hirshfeld⁴⁶ partitioning (TS/HI)^{47,48}, many-body dispersion energy^{49,50} with fractionally ionic model for polarizability⁵¹ method (MBD/FI)⁵², and density-dependent energy correction dDsC⁵³, as implemented in VASP^{47,48,52,54–56}. Geometry optimizations were carried out using an external optimizer GADGET^{57,58} until the atomic forces on each atom were less than 0.005^{-3} eV/Å. The vibrational frequencies calculations were performed numerically using central differences with the numerical step of 0.02 Å.

In the relaxations performed within the initial screening of dispersion correction methods (see Section III A), conventional unit cells containing 20 atoms and the k -points grids of $4 \times 8 \times 2$ (NL) and $4 \times 4 \times 4$ (DP) were employed. Consistent with our previous work⁷,

supercells consisting of $2 \times 4 \times 1$ (NL) and $2 \times 2 \times 2$ (DP) multiples of conventional unit cells containing 160 atoms each (see Fig. 1) were used in AIMD and all free energy calculations. In both cases, the Brillouin zone was sampled using grid of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ k -points, making the setting used in AIMD simulations consistent with that employed in relaxations with smaller structural models.

B. *NPT* and *NVT* AIMD and the machine learning force fields

Temperature dependent properties were investigated using AIMD accelerated by machine learning force fields (MLFF)^{59,60}, as implemented in VASP. These simulations were performed in *NPT* ensemble at temperatures 300 K, 600 K, 900 K and 1200 K. The simulation T was kept constant by employing Langevin thermostat^{61–63} with a friction coefficient of 2 ps^{-1} for all atoms. External pressure of 0 GPa was maintained by Parrinello–Rahman barostat.^{64,65} The equations of motion of the ions were integrated using velocity verlet algorithm³⁴ with a time step of 3 fs. A mass of 2 amu and a friction coefficient of 10 ps^{-1} were used for the lattice degrees of freedom.

The MLFF model for energy, forces, and stresses was trained using Bayesian regression.^{59,66} The training configurations were chosen automatically and on-the-fly during an AIMD run based on the similarity with other training configurations and quality of predictions of energies, forces, and stress tensor components.⁶⁷ In our calculations, a separate training for each phase and temperature was carried out with the initial Bayesian error threshold of $0.01 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$. The training typically consisted of 2×10^4 MD steps. The quality of the MLFF is evaluated in Section SIV of Supplementary Material. Post training, a production run of length 3 ns was performed in *NPT* ensemble by employing the learned force fields. Observables such as the lattice parameters, volume and energy, were obtained as ensemble averages after discarding the data corresponding to equilibration, which was determined using the Mann-Kendall test^{68–70} for trend in mean and variance. The MD simulations performed within the thermodynamic integration (see section III B 3) were performed in the *NVT* ensemble using the MLFF trained in *NPT* MD at the same temperature. The thermostat setting and the integration step were the same as in the *NPT* simulations. The length of the trajectories produced for different λ values (vide infra) was 100 ps.

C. Notation used in this work

In the following text, k_B , and \hbar are the Boltzmann and the reduced Planck constants, respectively, \mathbf{s} represents the vector of atomic positions expressed in fractional coordinates, \mathbf{h} is the lattice matrix defined using the lattice vectors of the supercell ($\mathbf{a}_i; i = 1, 2, 3$) as $\mathbf{h} = \{\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \mathbf{a}_3\}$. The atomic positions and cell geometries obtained in relaxations at a fixed supercell volume $V = |\det\{\mathbf{h}\}|$ are indicated as \mathbf{s}_V and \mathbf{h}_V , respectively, whereby symbol $V_0(T)$ is reserved for the ground state cell volume at the temperature T . The term $\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}$ is used for the NPT ensemble average of \mathbf{h} evaluated for specific values of P and T , and $\mathbf{s}_{\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}}$ indicates relaxed atomic positions for the cell geometry given by $\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}$. Finally, $\omega_p(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})$ and $A_{el}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})$ are, respectively, the harmonic frequency of the phonon branch p and the electronic free energy computed for the structure given by \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{h} . Note that for a singlet state (all systems discussed in this work), $A_{el}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})$ corresponds to the electronic energy ($E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})$) obtained in a QM calculation based on the Born-Oppenheimer approximation.

III. RESULTS

A. Initial screening of dispersion correction methods

As discussed in section I, long range dispersion interactions are essential to accurately measure both the structure and energies of perovskite materials. Before starting the time consuming free energy calculations, it is therefore useful to screen the dispersion correction methods for the best performance in static 0 K calculations. To proceed systematically, we tested all the methods presently available in VASP that can be linked with the PBE functional (see Section II A). As a screening criterion, lowest maximum error in computed lattice geometry determined with experimental reference¹⁴ is used. In addition, we also require that the chosen method predicts a lower potential energy for the relaxed NL structure, which is experimentally known to be stable at low values of T . This requirement is motivated by the fact that, as we shall show in Section III B, the thermal and entropic effects stabilize the DP structure relative to NL, i.e., only a method that predicts a lower energy for the relaxed NL can be consistent with the observed low T phase stability.

As reference, we use sets of lattice constants $a=8.525 \text{ \AA}$, $b=3.826 \text{ \AA}$, $c=13.925 \text{ \AA}$ (NL), and $a=7.108 \text{ \AA}$, $b=9.772 \text{ \AA}$, and $c=6.741 \text{ \AA}$ (DP) determined experimentally¹⁴ at the room temperature. To facilitate comparison with structural data obtained in structural relaxations, the experimental data were extrapolated to 0 K using the thermal expansion coefficients (TEC) determined in our previous AIMD study⁶, which results in $a=8.509 \text{ \AA}$, $b=3.806 \text{ \AA}$, $c=13.834 \text{ \AA}$ (NL), and $a=7.098 \text{ \AA}$, $b=9.731 \text{ \AA}$, $c=6.704 \text{ \AA}$ (DP). We note that the result of extrapolation is almost independent of the dispersion correction used in the TEC calculations.⁶

Fig. 2 shows the relative error in lattice constants with respect to experimental reference computed for various correction methods and the corresponding numerical values of lattice constants are listed in Table S1 in the supplementary material. The largest relative errors obtained using the uncorrected PBE functional for the NL and DP phase are 1.6 and 1.4 %, respectively. The correction methods D3(0), D3(BJ), dDsC, and TS/HI systematically improve the quality of prediction for all three lattice parameters so that the absolute maximum errors do not exceed 0.7 % (D3(0)), 1.0 % (D3(BJ)), 0.5 % (dDsC) and 0.4 % (TS/HI) for NL and 0.6 % (D3(0)), 0.4 % (D3(BJ) and dDsC) and 0.3 % (TS/HI) for DP. Another reasonably well performing method is D2, which improves all parameters except c of the NL phase, with the maximum relative errors being 1.4 % (NL) and 0.7 % (DP). The remaining two methods degrade the quality of predictions for one (TS) or both (MBD/FI) phases as compared to the uncorrected PBE results. The computed energy differences between the NL and DP phases obtained using different methods are also shown in Fig. 2. Positive values of $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP} = E(DP) - E(NL)$ are predicted by all methods except D3(0) and TS.

Altogether, the correction methods D3(BJ), dDsC and TS/HI systematically improve upon the uncorrected PBE predictions for all lattice parameters of both phases of SrZrS₃ considered here and, at the same time, predict correct stability order for the NL and DP phases. Since the performance of the TS/HI is clearly the best of all the methods tested, we opted to use it in the thermodynamic calculations presented in section III B.

FIG. 2. Relative errors with respect to reference experimental values¹⁴ extrapolated to 0 K (in %) for the lattice constants (a , b , c) of (a) NL and (b) DP phases of SrZrS₃, and (c) zero temperature ground state energy difference between the NL and DP phases ($\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP} = E_{NL} - E_{DP}$) obtained from structural relaxations using different dispersion corrections. Note that a positive value of $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ implies that the NL phase is more stable than the DP at 0 K.

B. Simulations of relative stability of NL and DP phases

Having established the superior performance of the TS/Hi method compared to other dispersion correction methods at 0 K, we now employ this approach to access the relative stability of the NL and DP phases of SrZrS₃ at thermodynamic conditions given by external pressure (P) and thermodynamic temperature (T). The relevant thermodynamic potential to be analysed is the Gibbs free energy (G).⁷¹ In particular, the positive value of the differences between G computed for the NL and for the DP phases ($G_{DP} - G_{NL}$) indicates that the NL phase is stable, the negative value corresponds to conditions where DP is stable, while the vanishing value is achieved when the two phases are at equilibrium and the corresponding T at a fixed P corresponds to the temperature of phase transition ($T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$).

In order to access G in computer simulations, it is usually more convenient to determine Helmholtz free energies (A) and employ the thermodynamic relation⁷¹

$$G(T, P) = A(T, V(P)) + PV(P), \quad (1)$$

where $V(P)$ is the value of volume evaluated for a particular value of P . In this work, $P = 0$ is considered, simplifying eq. 1 to identity $G(T, P) = A(T, V(P))$. To obtain an insight into different contributions to $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$, we examined a hierarchy of methods for the calculation of A .

1. Harmonic approximation

Within the semi-classical harmonic approximation (HA), the Helmholtz free energy of a crystalline system writes

$$A_{HA}(T) = A_{el}(\mathbf{s}_{V_0(T=0K)}, \mathbf{h}_{V_0(T=0K)}) - k_B T \sum_{p=1}^{3N-3} \ln \frac{k_B T}{\hbar \omega_p(\mathbf{s}_{V_0(T=0K)}, \mathbf{h}_{V_0(T=0K)})} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of atoms in the supercell that must be chosen so as to achieve convergence of A_{HA} per a formula unit (f.u.). Importantly, the frequencies are independent of the cell geometry within this approximation. Consequently, the harmonic crystal does not expand and A_{HA} depends only on T . We note that we chose to use semi-classical statistical mechanics expressions in this work for consistency with AIMD calculations employed at certain stages of our calculations (*vide infra*), which also generates semi-classical ensembles. However, as we show in Section SII of supplementary material, replacing eq. 2 by its quantum mechanical analogue has only small effect on the quality of our results.

According to our HA calculations, the NL phase is stable up to $T_{NL \rightarrow DP} = 824$ K (see Fig. 3), while the DP phase dominates at higher temperatures. Since the difference in the electronic contribution to enthalpic difference ($H_{NL \rightarrow DP}$) remains fixed at $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP} = 0.092$ eV/f.u. and the difference in the vibrational contributions to $H_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ vanishes at all temperatures (by equipartition principle, classical vibrational enthalpy of harmonic system equals $3Nk_B T$), the thermal stabilization of the DP phase is entirely entropic in nature and, qualitatively, originates in generally lower phonon frequencies of most of vibrational modes of DP⁷². Within the HA, the term $-T\Delta S_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ decreases with T approximately linearly, from -0.034 eV/f.u. at 300 K to -0.102 eV/f.u. at 900 K.

FIG. 3. Free energy difference between the DP and NL phase ($\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$) in the temperature range 0-900 K determined using PBE+TS/HI functionals. Transition temperatures obtained using harmonic (HA), static quasi-harmonic (S-QHA), quasi-harmonic performed with structures from *NPT* AIMD (AIMD-QHA), and fully anharmonic thermodynamic integration (TI) are determined as temperatures for which the phase equilibrium condition $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP} = 0$ is fulfilled.

2. Quasi-harmonic approximations

Within the quasi-harmonic approximation¹⁶ (QHA), a part of anharmonicity is taken into account via implicit dependence of harmonic frequencies on the cell geometry given by \mathbf{h} . In the simplest approach, which we denote here the static QHA (S-QHA),^{18,19} a series of structures with \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{h} relaxed for a range of fixed cell volumes is considered, making the computed Helmholtz free energy:

$$A_{QHA}(T, V) = A_{el}(\mathbf{s}_V, \mathbf{h}_V) - k_B T \sum_{p=1}^{3N-3} \ln \frac{k_B T}{\hbar \omega_p(\mathbf{s}_V, \mathbf{h}_V)} \quad (3)$$

explicitly volume dependent. In our calculations, a series of 13 regularly spaced values of V were considered from the interval $0.94 V_0 \leq V \leq 1.12 V_0$. The corresponding atomic positions and lattice geometries were relaxed, vibrational analyses were performed, and $A_{QHA}(T, V)$ values were determined for all relevant temperatures. For each T , the resulting $A_{QHA}(T, V)$ versus V dependence was then fitted by the Murnaghan⁷³ EOS with the ground state free energy ($A_{QHA}(T, V_0(T))$), ground state volume ($V_0(T)$), bulk modulus ($B_0(T)$) at zero pressure and its pressure derivative ($B'_0(T)$) being the fitting parameters.

Finally, the cell geometry corresponding to the cell volume of $V_0(T)$ was obtained from dependencies of lattice constant on V via interpolation .

The T dependencies of lattice parameters of the NL and DP phases computed using S-QHA are shown in Fig. 4. As evident, S-QHA predicts a monotonous and approximately linear increase of all lattice parameters with T and qualitatively the same behaviour is observed for both phases. The monotonously growing deviation of the finite- T structures from the 0 K structure considered in the HA approach causes the computed G_{QHA} to deviate from G_{HA} and the difference increases with T . In the case of the NL phase, the computed anharmonicity ($G_{QHA} - G_{HA}$) is -0.004 eV/f.u. at 300 K and -0.041 eV/f.u. at 900 K, while for the DP structure the values of -0.004 eV/f.u. (300 K) and -0.038 eV/f.u. (900 K) were obtained. The term $-T\Delta S_{NL\rightarrow DP}$ decreases from -0.034 to -0.094 eV/f.u. over the interval 300 to 900 K, i.e., the entropic stabilization of DP is slightly weaker compared to the HA prediction. This is, however, partly compensated by the electronic contribution to $\Delta H_{NL\rightarrow DP}$, which, due to variable cell shape, decreases at 900 K from 0.092 eV/f.u. (HA) to 0.088 eV/f.u. (S-QHA). Thus, the part of anharmonicity that is taken into account within the S-QHA has a rather modest impact on the value of $T_{NL\rightarrow DP}$, which is predicted to be 851 K, i.e, 27 K higher compared to the HA prediction (see Fig. 3).

Clearly, the S-QHA approach assumes that all the thermally induced cell shape changes are fully determined by the dependence of \mathbf{h} on V at zero T . This serious restriction, causing that the S-QHA is inherently unable to describe T -dependent anisotropy in thermal expansion, can be lifted by combining QHA with AIMD in NPT ensemble, which fully accounts for anharmonicity effects on the structure. Within this approach, which we denote AIMD-QHA, the Helmholtz free energy is determined using

$$A_{QHA}(T, \langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}) = A_{el}(\mathbf{s}_{\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}}, \langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}) - k_B T \sum_{p=1}^{3N-3} \ln \frac{k_B T}{\hbar \omega_p(\mathbf{s}_{\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}}, \langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T})}, \quad (4)$$

where the ensemble averages $\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}$ are obtained from the MLFF-accelerated NPT AIMD described in Sec. II B.

Thermal variation of the lattice constants computed using AIMD-QHA are compared with the S-QHA results in Fig. 4. In case of the NL phase, both methods predict qualitatively similar trends with a nearly linear increase of all lattice constants. The two methods are also in semi-quantitative agreement, whereby the AIMD-QHA predicts slightly lower slope for the increase of a and higher slope for the increase of b with T . At 900 K, where

FIG. 4. Comparison of the thermal variation of scaled lattice parameters for a) the NL ($a' = a/2$, $b' = b$, $c' = c/4$) and b) DP ($a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$) phases of SrZrS_3 obtained at the PBE+TS/HI level using the S-QHA (denoted by dashed lines) and *NPT* AIMD (denoted by solid lines) approaches.

the deviation between structural predictions of both methods is the largest, the AIMD-QHA method yields the lattice parameters a , b , and c that differ by -0.83 %, 0.44 %, and 0.16% from those obtained by S-QHA, while the difference in V is -0.26 %. Consequently, G_{QHA} computed using both methods are very similar, (see Tab. S2 in supplementary material). A more significant difference in structure is observed for the DP phase, where AIMD-QHA predicts deviations from the quasi-linear increase of a , b , c , and V obtained using S-QHA by -1.07 %, 0.13%, 0.41 %, and -0.58 %. As discussed in detail in our previ-

ous works^{6,7}, the structural changes of the lattice geometry of DP with increasing T are due to a quasi-continuous transformation to the parent cubic phase (C). This is exactly a type of thermal effect that can not be described by the S-QHA approach and leads to more significant differences in G_{QHA} compared to the NL phase (see Tab. S2 in supplementary material). Since, compared to the S-QHA, the AIMD-QHA predicts lower $G_{QHA} - G_{HA}$ for DP (-0.040 eV/f.u. (AIMD-QHA) versus -0.038 eV/f.u. (S-QHA)) and almost the same values for NL (-0.041 eV/f.u. with both methods), $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ increases. Thus, surprisingly somewhat, the differences $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ computed via AIMD-QHA are virtually identical to the HA results over whole range of temperatures (see Table S2 in supplementary material), which is a consequence of compensation of anharmonic contributions of the $\Delta H_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ and $-T\Delta S_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ terms. At 900 K, for instance, anharmonicity contributes 0.007 eV/f.u. to $\Delta H_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ and 0.008 eV/f.u. to $-T\Delta S_{NL \rightarrow DP}$, leading to anharmonic $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP} = 0.001$ eV/f.u. Consequently, the AIMD-QHA prediction for $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ (826 K) is very similar to that obtained from HA (824 K), see Fig. 3.

3. Thermodynamic Integration (TI)

The QHA approaches are intrinsically unable to account for anharmonicity due to thermally-induced internal structure changes. In particular, the quasi-continuous transformation of DP to C (see section SIII in supplementary material) is associated with decrease of transversal displacement of S atoms from its ideal position in the middle of the Zr-Zr link (involving Zr-S bonds from ZrS_6 octahedra sharing a common atom S) from ~ 0.7 to 0.0 Å.⁶ However, the AIMD-QHA value of free energy can be corrected for the missing anharmonicity contribution via thermodynamic integration (TI) with harmonic reference.^{33,74,75} In this method, Helmholtz free energy of a fully interacting system (1) driven by Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_1 is expressed as follows:

$$A_1 = A_0 + \Delta A_{0 \rightarrow 1}, \quad (5)$$

where $A_0 = A_{QHA}(T, \langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T})$, determined using eq. 4, is the free energy of reference harmonic state (0) driven by the Hamiltonian \mathcal{H}_0 , and $\Delta A_{0 \rightarrow 1}$ is the free energy difference between systems 0 and 1 calculated as follows:

$$\Delta A_{0 \rightarrow 1} = \int_0^1 \langle E_1(\lambda) - E_0(\lambda) \rangle_\lambda d\lambda. \quad (6)$$

In eq. 6, the term $\langle \dots \rangle_\lambda$ represents the average of enclosed quantities over NVT ensemble generated by the Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H}_\lambda = \lambda \mathcal{H}_1 + (1 - \lambda) \mathcal{H}_0, \quad (7)$$

and λ is the coupling parameter.

We note that the state 0 can be chosen arbitrarily and does not need to correspond to the best harmonic approximation of the fully interacting system. Following Ref.⁷⁵, we defined the state 0 in terms of rotationally and translationally invariant internal coordinates (here a redundant set of interatomic distances was used) as follows. First, the atomic positions were relaxed while keeping the cell geometry fixed at $\langle \mathbf{h} \rangle_{P,T}$ obtained from NPT AIMD. Subsequently, the Hesse matrix was obtained via finite difference method, whereby the eigenvalues of this matrix that were lower than the limit $1 \text{ eV } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ were increased to that limit while keeping the eigenvectors unaltered. As discussed in Ref.⁷⁵, this procedure avoids numerical problems due to nonphysical configurations generated by \mathcal{H}_λ for low λ values. All these steps were performed at the DFT level using the setting described in Section II A. Finally, the Hesse matrix was expressed in internal coordinates which were employed in the TI calculations, see Ref.⁷⁵ for details.

Integration in eq. 6 was realized numerically by the method proposed in Ref.⁷⁶ that is based on Bennett acceptance ratio approach⁷⁷. A regular grid of 5 λ points including the two integration limits was used for that purpose. The calculations of $\langle E_1(\lambda) - E_0(\lambda) \rangle_\lambda$ were performed in NVT ensemble using the MLFF obtained in previous NPT MD runs at the same T (see Section II B), whereby the lengths of production runs was 450 ps for each value of λ .

Since the MLFF represents an approximation to true DFT potential energy landscape, our MLFF-based TI calculations are biased to some extent. To correct for the error introduced by MLFF, free energy perturbation theory^{78–80} (FEPT) was used, whereby the corrected Helmholtz free energy ($A_{1,DFT}$) was obtained from the MLFF value ($A_{1,MLFF}$) as follows:

$$A_{1,DFT} = A_{1,MLFF} - k_B T \ln \{ \langle \exp[-\Delta E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h}) / k_B T] \rangle_{MLFF} \}. \quad (8)$$

In eq. 8, the term $\langle \dots \rangle_{MLFF}$ is the NVT ensemble average generated by the Hamiltonian corresponding to MLFF and $\Delta E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h}) = E_{DFT}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h}) - E_{MLFF}(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})$ is the potential energy difference between DFT and MLFF computed for the configuration with atomic positions

s and lattice geometry \mathbf{h} . In the calculations of $\langle \exp[-\Delta E(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{h})/k_B T] \rangle_{MLFF}$, second-order cumulant expansion⁷⁹ employing 250 configurations randomly chosen from the trajectory generated in TI with $\lambda=1$ was used.

Taking full anharmonicity into account leads to stabilization of both the NL and DP phases. Nevertheless, the term $G_{TI} - G_{HA}$ computed for NL is greater in absolute value (-0.048 eV/f.u. (NL) versus -0.043 eV/f.u. (DP)). Thus, anharmonicity stabilizes the NL relative to the DP phase, which can be intuitively understood because the former structure consists of one-dimensional ZrS_3 chains that are not connected by covalent bonds and are therefore less accurately described by the harmonic model than the fully connected 3D framework of the DP structure (see Fig. 1). This additional stabilization leads to an increase in the predicted transition temperature from 827 K obtained in AIMD-QHA calculations to 867 K (see Fig. 3). Altogether, our best estimate of the anharmonicity effect on $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$, obtained by comparing the HA and TI values, is 43 K.

IV. DISCUSSION

According to experiment¹⁴, both the NL and the DP phases can exist at ambient conditions but the NL \rightarrow DP phase transition occurs when the T of the former is increased to 1250 K. This process can be reversed, whereby the DP phase is fully transformed into NL when heated to 1020 K¹⁴. The presence of hysteresis in experimental thermochemical data indicates that the observed phase transitions followed irreversible transformation paths and hence the reported transition temperatures should be interpreted only as upper and lower bounds for the $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ determined for ideal reversible process considered in our work. Our best estimate of $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}=867$ K obtained in fully anharmonic treatment of atomic and lattice degrees of freedom therefore underestimates experimental transition T by at least 150 K. Although this error might seem large, our result still represents a significant improvement compared to previous theoretical report of Koocher et al.⁷² based on self-consistent QHA calculations performed at the PBEsol⁸¹ level, that underestimated $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ by at least 430 K. We note, however, that the seemingly large error in theoretical predictions is mainly due to the very similar free energies of the NL and DP phases (see Tab. S2 in supplementary material) and only small differences in the slopes of their T dependencies, which makes theoretical results very sensitive on the choice of simulation

methodology. In our work, we have shown that various types of anharmonic effects, such as thermal expansion of cell volume, or thermally induced cell shape and internal structure changes, have only a relatively modest effect (within 50 K) on predicted $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$. Thus, the choice of the electronic structure method, directly affecting both the electronic energy and harmonic frequencies, turns out to be the most important factor in accurate calculations. To this end, we have shown that just the dispersion correction linked with the same functional (PBE) leads to variations in $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ between -0.121 (PBE+TS) and 0.099 eV/f.u. (PBE+D2), which, assuming that all the thermal and entropic effects are similar to those explicitly explored in this work using the PBE+TS/HI methods, would translate into $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ between 0 and 900 K. Using the same assumption, we estimate that an ideal electronic structure method should yield $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ between 0.110 and 0.150 eV/f.u., which might serve, together with the accuracy in structural predictions, as criterion in the future screening studies involving multiple functionals and/or post-DFT treatments. The fact that the lower bound of the ideal $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ is just 0.018 eV/f.u. higher than the value of 0.093 meV/f.u. obtained by the PBE+TS/HI identified in this work as the best for describing the structure of both phases, illustrates the sensitivity of the problem.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A systematic investigation on the thermally driven NL to DP phase transition of SrZrS₃ was performed by means of free energy calculations at various levels of complexity. The quality of various dispersion correction schemes for the PBE functional (D2, D3(0), D3(BJ), TS, TS/HI, MBD-FI, and dDsC) was evaluated to determine their ability to predict the ground state geometries and potential energy differences of the NL and DP phases in agreement with available experimental data. Based on the the results of our screening, the TS/HI correction was identified as the best, predicting correct zero- T relative stability of DP and NL phases and the lattice geometries with error within 0.4 % for both phases. The PBE+TS/HI was subsequently used in thermodynamic calculations.

Free energy calculations were performed to determine relative stability of the NL and DP phases of SrZrS₃ at various temperatures and determine the transition T . In order to investigate the effect of different types of anharmonicity, a hierarchy of methods was

used in the calculations. A simple harmonic approximation that ignores the thermal expansion of the lattice provided us with a reference to determine the magnitude of the anharmonicity. The value of $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ obtained using this approach is 824 K. The static quasi-harmonic approximation takes into account a part of anharmonicity via implicit dependence of harmonic frequencies on the cell volume determined for a series of relaxed structures. Applying this approach led to increase of $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ to 851 K.

The assumption of the S-QHA that the lattice geometry changes are fully fixed by volume can be lifted by applying the quasi harmonic approximation for relaxed structures with lattice geometries obtained as ensemble averages from NPT AIMD. This part of anharmonicity has a more significant impact on the structure of the DP phase, which is primarily due to the tendency of DP to transform into parent cubic phase when T is increased^{6,7}. Hence, unsurprisingly, this effect decreased free energy of DP more than that of NL, shifting thus $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ to lower value (826 K) compared to the S-QHA result.

Since both the S-QHA and AIMD-QHA approach calculations are performed for structures with relaxed atomic positions, they inherently fail to account for the anharmonicity associated with thermally induced internal structure changes. Starting from the AIMD-QHA results, this additional contribution can be taken into account using thermodynamic integration with harmonic reference. Compared to AIMD-QHA, TI leads to stronger stabilization of the NL structure, which is related to the fact that it consists of 1D chains of ZrS_3 that are not bound by covalent bonds and are therefore less accurately described by the harmonic model than the fully connected 3D framework of the DP phase. Consequently, the transition temperature calculated at the TI level is shifted to a higher value of 867 K as compared to the AIMD-QHA prediction.

In comparison with experiment¹⁴, our best theoretical prediction based on TI is at least 150 K lower but still represents a significant improvement over the previous theoretical report of Koocher et al.⁷² that underestimated $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ by at least 430 K. The main reason that complicates accurate theoretical predictions is the similarity in stability of both phases and in the slope of corresponding G versus T curves. Comparison of our TI and HA result suggests that the anharmonicity effect on $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ is rather modest (43 K), and therefore the choice of the electronic structure method is a key factor that needs to be improved in future work. Based on our results we estimate that an ideal electronic structure method should yield $\Delta E_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ between 0.110 and 0.150 eV/f.u.. This proposed range

of values can serve as one of criteria in the future screening studies involving multiple functionals and/or post-DFT treatments.

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